

Opportunities for Data Exchange

THE ODE PROJECT / FUNDERS

Opportunities for Data Sharing

There is a growing consensus in science, and society generally, that primary research data resulting from publicly funded research should be shared widely so that the maximum benefits can be gained from the investment. There are common barriers and some reluctance, but also powerful drivers and benefits related to putting this general principle into practice.

Why should you as a research policy maker or funder care about data sharing?

There are variations in the maturity of data sharing across different communities, but leading examples such as the Worldwide Protein Data Bank, Pangaea and GenBank show that supporting the technical and human infrastructure of data sharing will increase the benefits and outcomes of research funding across all disciplines.

Do you know about others' views?

The EU FP7-funded ODE project has collected views from numerous individuals – representative of all stakeholder groups involved – on the opportunities for data exchange. These views were analysed and consolidated in order to inform each group about each others' views and possible future activities.

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What ODE has learned:

Researchers have to balance priorities of data management and sharing with pressures such as publication of papers. For this reason they need clear incentives and rewards for data sharing.

Libraries and data centres observe that taking steps towards early data preservation reduces long-term costs, and that data regeneration is more expensive than data preservation.

Publishers have a major role to play in encouraging the creation, support and use of infrastructures and services that allow data to be shared and discovered. Publishing data alongside articles adds value and the sustainable solution lies in the distributed data infrastructure that enables co-operation with data centres, and the development of data aggregation and discovery services.

What you and your organization can do:

Funding agencies and policy makers should seek to promote explicit funding for data management in research grants, and co-ordinate policies with other funders and across disciplines. This could extend to requiring data management plans for the deposit and preservation of citable data sets as part of research proposals.

You can declare the importance of data as a measure of academic prestige, and consider ways of taking data into account as well as publications when planning research evaluations. Such evaluations can be based on explicit research data transparency and audit policies.

You can ensure funding for co-ordinated development and maintenance of basic institutional or discipline-based infrastructures, and fund the corresponding service development.

Higher education providers can be encouraged to include data skills training in postgraduate courses.

Data is the new gold.

"We have a huge goldmine ... Let's start mining it."

Neelie Kroes, Vice-President of the European Commission responsible for the Digital Agenda
<http://europa.eu/rapid/pressReleasesAction.do?reference=SPEECH/11/872&type=HTML>

The research results of this project are co-funded by the European Commission under the FP7 Research Infrastructures Grant Agreement Nr. 261530.

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